

Effects of salt and monosodium glutamate on the sensory acceptance of low-sodium cheese-flavoured corn grits expanded snacks

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Abstract

The reduction of salt content in foods is not a simple task because sodium compounds play an important role in the flavour of foods. Thus, we evaluated the effects of salt and monosodium glutamate on the sensory acceptance of cheese-flavoured corn grits expanded snacks, looking at reducing sodium content of these products. The addition of salt and monosodium glutamate was performed based on the Response Surface Methodology, having the addition of salt (0.20, 0.35, 0.70, 1.05 and 1.20%) and addition of monosodium glutamate (0.18, 0.30, 0.60, 0.90 and 1.02%) as independent variables. The snacks were evaluated through the Just-About-Right scale and the structured hedonic scale (both of nine points). An increase in the percentage of salt increased the ideal of intensity of salty taste, the degree of liking of salty taste and the degree of liking of flavour, while an increase in the monosodium glutamate percentage increased only the first two previous sensory responses. No interactions were observed between salt and monosodium glutamate. Among the snacks studied, that with 1.2% salt and 0.6% monosodium glutamate stands out, since it was sensorially accepted and still had estimated sodium content below the average for commercial snacks. Concluding, our results are relevant for providing alternatives for reducing the sodium content on products; the reduction, however, must be gradual so as not to negatively affect consumer acceptance.

Keywords: thermoplastic extrusion, sensory acceptance, sodium

Introduction

The reduction of sodium content in foods is not a simple task because sodium ions play an important role in the flavour of foods. Among products with high salt content, expanded snacks often spring to mind. Such products have both high fat and salt content, being regarded as highly energetic and nutritionally poor [1], reasons because they are highly criticized [2]. Despite this, the snack market has been gaining prominence due to the consumer search for practical and fast food. The thermoplastic extrusion is used for many varied products in the food industry because of its high versatility and flexibility, with expanded corn snacks standing out. The combination of practicality and the tendency to consume healthier foods leads to the need to increase the production of snacks with lower sodium content. Therefore, we aimed to assess the effects of salt and monosodium glutamate on the sensory acceptance of cheese-flavoured corn grits expanded snacks, aiming to reduce the sodium content of these products.

Experimental

Corn grits with 15% moisture (wet basis) were extruded in an RXPQ Labor 24 single screw extruder (INBRAMAQ, Ribeirão Preto, Brazil) with five independent heating zones. The extrusion conditions were: three helicoidally grooved barrel; screw with a large step of one exit with a compression ratio of 2.3:1 and length-to-diameter ratio of 15.5:1; pre-die extruder with holes of 3.01 mm; extruder die with a diameter of 2.93 mm (round hole); feed rate of 265 g/min; screw speed at 237 rpm; temperatures in zones 1 to 5: off (around 25 °C), 70 °C, 90 °C, 140 °C and 140 °C respectively.

A mixture of 6% of sunflower oil, 1.5% of cheese aroma, salt and monosodium glutamate was used for extrudate flavouring. The sunflower oil quantity was defined based on a previous study [3], while the quantity of cheese aroma was recommended by the donor company of the aroma. The addition of salt and monosodium glutamate was performed based on the Response Surface Methodology, through a rotational central composite design for two independent variables with five levels each: addition of salt (0.20, 0.35, 0.70, 1.05 and 1.20%) and addition of monosodium glutamate (0.18, 0.30, 0.60, 0.90 and 1.02%), both in percentages related to 100 g of extrudate. Twelve assays were performed: four assays of factorial points (2²), four assays of axial points and four repetitions of the central point. The dependent variables were: 1) acceptance of cheese odour, salty taste and cheese

flavour using the Just-About-Right scale of nine points, and 2) acceptance of odour, salty taste, and flavour, as well as overall acceptance, using the nine-point structured hedonic scale. Sixty-three consumers were recruited.

Linear and quadratic models were tested to explain the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variables using the Minitab 17 software (Minitab Inc.). The results were then subjected to multiple regression analysis and coefficients of the model with p-values ≤ 0.05 were considered significant. Analysis of variance was applied and p-values ≤ 0.05 and > 0.05 were considered to evaluate the significance of regression and the lack of fit, respectively. Only models that were significant, with no lack of fit, and with R^2 higher than or equal to 70% are presented in this paper. The response surfaces were plotted using the Statistica 7.0 software (StatSoft Inc.).

Results and discussion

The intensity was 'slightly less than ideal' (means around 4) for cheese odour and between 'slightly and moderately less than ideal' for the salty taste and cheese flavour (means between 4 and 3, respectively) (Table 1). Moreover, the means of the degree of liking of odour, salty taste, flavour and overall acceptance of the snacks ranged from 'neither liked nor disliked' (score 5) to 'I liked it slightly' (score 6).

Table 1: Sensory acceptance of cheese-flavoured corn grits expanded snacks (mean \pm SD; n = 63).

assay	salt (%)	MSG (%)	JAR scale			hedonic scale			
			cheese odour	salty taste	cheese flavour	odour	salty taste	flavour	overall
1	0.35	0.30	4.0 \pm 1.4	3.3 \pm 1.5	3.4 \pm 1.4	5.9 \pm 1.8	5.1 \pm 1.9	5.3 \pm 1.9	5.4 \pm 1.7
2	1.05	0.30	4.3 \pm 1.3	3.6 \pm 1.3	3.8 \pm 1.3	6.3 \pm 1.8	5.6 \pm 1.8	6.1 \pm 1.7	6.0 \pm 1.7
3	0.35	0.90	4.3 \pm 1.5	3.9 \pm 1.6	4.1 \pm 1.8	6.3 \pm 1.6	5.3 \pm 1.8	5.7 \pm 1.8	5.9 \pm 1.6
4	1.05	0.90	4.1 \pm 1.3	3.9 \pm 1.4	3.9 \pm 1.5	6.0 \pm 1.9	5.6 \pm 1.8	6.0 \pm 2.0	6.0 \pm 1.9
5	0.20	0.60	4.0 \pm 1.5	3.2 \pm 1.5	3.3 \pm 1.6	5.8 \pm 1.8	4.8 \pm 1.8	5.0 \pm 1.7	5.2 \pm 1.7
6	1.20	0.60	4.1 \pm 1.5	3.9 \pm 1.6	3.7 \pm 1.6	6.1 \pm 1.7	5.8 \pm 1.9	5.9 \pm 1.7	6.0 \pm 1.6
7	0.70	0.18	4.1 \pm 1.5	3.5 \pm 1.5	3.6 \pm 1.6	6.0 \pm 1.8	5.0 \pm 1.7	5.4 \pm 1.8	5.5 \pm 1.7
8	0.70	1.02	4.3 \pm 1.2	4.2 \pm 1.5	4.0 \pm 1.5	6.4 \pm 1.7	5.7 \pm 1.8	5.9 \pm 1.7	6.0 \pm 1.5
9	0.70	0.60	3.9 \pm 1.5	3.7 \pm 1.5	3.6 \pm 1.5	5.8 \pm 1.7	5.3 \pm 1.8	5.6 \pm 1.8	5.5 \pm 1.7
10	0.70	0.60	4.0 \pm 1.5	3.7 \pm 1.7	3.7 \pm 1.7	6.1 \pm 2.1	5.3 \pm 2.0	5.5 \pm 2.1	5.5 \pm 2.0
11	0.70	0.60	4.1 \pm 1.3	3.7 \pm 1.4	3.5 \pm 1.6	6.0 \pm 1.6	5.7 \pm 1.6	5.7 \pm 1.7	5.8 \pm 1.5
12	0.70	0.60	4.2 \pm 1.6	3.7 \pm 1.6	3.5 \pm 1.6	6.0 \pm 1.8	5.4 \pm 1.9	5.6 \pm 1.9	5.8 \pm 1.7

MSG = monosodium glutamate.

The independent variables influenced the ideal of intensity of salty taste and the degrees of liking of salty taste and flavour (Table 2). The increase in the salt percentage or the increase in the monosodium glutamate percentage increased the ideal of intensity of salty taste and the degree of liking of the salty taste. Only the response surface for the ideal of intensity of salty taste is presented here (Figure 1), since the surfaces for ideal of intensity of salty taste and for degree of liking of salty taste are all similar. The increase in the salt percentage increased the degree of liking of flavour (Table 2 and Figure 2).

Table 2: Models and goodness of fit for the dependent variables.

Dependent variable	Model	R ² adjusted (%)	p-value	p of lack of fit
Ideal of intensity of salty taste	$Y_{IIST} = 6.0423 + 0.2662X_1 + 0.2466X_2$	77.48	<0.001	0.332
Degree of liking of salty taste	$Y_{DLST} = 5.3730 + 0.2724X_1 + 0.1616X_2$	70.04	0.002	0.568
Degree of liking of flavour	$Y_{DLF} = 5.6217 + 0.2825X_1$	69.86	0.002	0.157

X_1 = salt (%), X_2 = monosodium glutamate (%).

Figure 1: Ideal of intensity of salty taste in function of the addition of salt or the addition of monosodium glutamate (both independent variables are as coded variables).

Figure 2: Degree of liking of flavour in function of the addition of salt (both independent variables are as coded variables).

The most interesting result and different from the expected is that there was no interaction between the independent variables; that is, the long-awaited 'flavour enhancing' effect of monosodium glutamate was not observed. Some authors [4] described that the ability of monosodium glutamate to be a flavour enhancer may be dependent on the particular flavour of interest. Additionally, we may raise a hypothesis that probably interaction between salt and monosodium glutamate and their effects on the sensory characteristics may be dependent also on the food matrix and the kind of food.

The monosodium glutamate did not have an effect on the degree of liking of flavour, although had affected the acceptance of salty taste as well as the salt (Table 2). Considering that monosodium glutamate has less sodium than salt (approximately 123 mg and 393 mg of sodium, respectively) [5], this can be a way of reducing sodium in this type of product, and monosodium glutamate is scientifically recognized as safe [6, 7].

Among the snacks studied, that with 1.2% salt and 0.6% monosodium glutamate (assay 6 of Table 1) stands out, once it is in the regions of higher acceptance both in Figures 1 and 2, is sensorially accepted (6.0 in the nine-point hedonic scale for overall liking; Table 1) and still has estimated sodium content below (123.9 mg Na/25 g snack) the average for commercial snacks available in the local market (from 87 to 298 mg Na/25 g snack).

Conclusion

The increase in the salt percentage increased the ideal of intensity of salty taste, the degree of liking of the salty taste and the degree of liking of flavour, while the increase in the monosodium glutamate percentage increased only the first two sensory responses. No interactions were observed between salt and monosodium glutamate considering results from Response Surface Methodology. Our results are relevant for providing alternatives for

reducing the sodium content on expanded snacks. Nevertheless, the reduction must be gradual so as not to negatively affect consumer acceptance.

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